

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH IN EDUCATION TODAY, PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS.

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Annotation. This article describes the role of English, which is widely used in the world, in our country, the current problems of its introduction into the education system and ways to solve them.

Keywords: Education system, personnel, foreign countries, teaching methods, necessary literature, various materials, outdated methods, the Soviet Union.

Since Uzbekistan's independence, many areas have been radically reformed, including education. In particular, the teaching process, textbooks, teacher qualifications, etc. have gradually changed and continue to change. Special attention was paid to foreign language teaching. The main reason for this is that many countries around the world use English.

As mentioned above, teaching and radically changing foreign languages was not an easy task, first of all it was necessary to increase the number of teachers. English, in particular, was and still is important. English is taught and widely used in many countries around the world.

In this regard, it is worth recalling the words of Islam Karimov: "Everyone cannot build their future without knowing their history."

Now, if we look at the importance of learning English, we can see that knowing English opens up great opportunities for us. Half a century ago, English was one of the most accepted international languages in the world. Over time, the role of the English language in society has increased significantly. Almost every adult in the world dreams of learning the basics of oral and written English. On top of that, they want their children to be fluent in the English they speak. There are many reasons for this. First, wherever we go, most likely people know the language. Whether it's a European country or an Asian or African country, if everyone explains what you're looking for in English, people will understand you. Second, almost all businesses in the world today are conducted in English. Basically, every field requires knowledge of this language. Students know that English plays an important role in their education and future endeavors. Professionals know that if they learn English at least intermediate level, they can get a big salary and advance in a fast career. Third, many books and periodicals are written in English. Most websites and pages are written in English. And all computer programs and applications use English. From the beginning of the emergence of computers in society, English began to be used as the main language. Many popular

movies and songs are in English. This list could go on indefinitely, but most importantly, in modern society, everyone understands how important English is today. Today, English is the mother tongue of more than 400 million people living in 12 countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand. It also ranks first in the world among foreign languages taught in high schools and high school, adult education clubs and courses. In France, public high schools require students to study English or German for four years, with the majority - at least 85% - choosing English. In Japan, students are required to study English for six years before graduating from high school. English ranks first in the world among foreign languages taught in secondary and high schools, as well as in various courses of the adult education system. In Russia, for example, about 70 percent of students with secondary and higher education study English. In a public opinion poll in Germany, 45 percent of respondents said they spoke English. In Italy, knowledge of English seems to be a prerequisite for occupying many positions related to the operation of modern technology. Knowledge of English is becoming commonplace for scientific and technical intellectuals in many developed countries. It is the main means of communication in the relations of foreign tourists with staff on all continents. Today, about 1 billion people, or one-fifth of the planet's population, speak English to one degree or another. Almost all major libraries have books in English. Detectives, novels, poems and other works can be read in the original in a foreign language. It is no secret that the translation of books is not always accurate and oral. The originals of the technical literature are no less. Thanks to your knowledge of English, you can learn more about the tools or equipment you are interested in it.

In turn, we can see that there are many challenges in teaching English and improving the literacy of students. In particular, the lack of qualified personnel, the lack or absence of modern technologies, the lack of necessary materials, the theft of students' time by teaching unnecessary subjects, and other problems.

How can we solve these problems? How can we improve the quality of education? As for the first problem, no one gives us the necessary personnel on our own, so we need to ensure that they are trained abroad, in developed countries. We know that in Uzbekistan, a large part of the population is middle-class and does not have enough money to improve their skills. However, many gifted students are children of the average person. We need to make it easy for them to read.

The second problem is that we have to buy modern technologies through our foreign partners. It may cost a lot of money, but our young people will definitely pay us back in excess.

As for the third problem, it is very relevant for students like us. That is, teaching unnecessary subjects and spending students' time on unnecessary subjects. To solve this problem, it is necessary to move to a credit-module system. In this system, only the subjects are selected according to the student's field, and the student has the opportunity to study only the subjects he / she needs.

Conclusion

From the above information, we can understand that English is one of the most needed languages and we can have great potential if we master this language perfectly. English is the language of the world and it is our responsibility to learn it.

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